

पेटेंट कार्यालय
शासकीय जर्नल

**OFFICIAL JOURNAL
OF
THE PATENT OFFICE**

निर्गमन सं. 33/2022
ISSUE NO. 33/2022

शुक्रवार
FRIDAY

दिनांक: 19/08/2022
DATE: 19/08/2022

पेटेंट कार्यालय का एक प्रकाशन
PUBLICATION OF THE PATENT OFFICE

(54) Title of the invention : HYBRID NANOCOMPOSITES, POLYMER COMPOSITES COMPRISING THE SAME AND FABRICATION TECHNIQUES THEREOF

(51) International classification :C08K0003040000, C08J0005000000, C08K0007240000, B29C0070080000, G01N0003420000

(86) International Application No :NA
 Filing Date :NA

(87) International Publication No : NA

(61) Patent of Addition to Application Number :NA
 Filing Date :NA

(62) Divisional to Application Number :NA
 Filing Date :NA

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(57) Abstract :
 Graphene (Gr) and Multiwall carbon nanotube (MWCNT)are evolutionary kind of nanofiller that has a number of desirable qualities. These attributes include remarkable capabilities and good compatibility with the majority of polymers. In this investigation, Graphene/MWCNT was used to strengthen the Jute mat fibre/epoxy composites in order to improve the hardness of these materials, its hardness values were studied. This research was undertaken with the intention of presenting a way for improving the hardness characteristics of composites for use in practical applications. The findings presented here may point the way to an important new direction of making fibre-reinforced thermoset composites that are reinforced with nanofillers and have a superior hardness value.

Fig : 1

No. of Pages : 11 No. of Claims : 10